

EFFECT OF NANOCLAY ON FIRE PERFORMANCE OF HYBRID NANO COMPOSITES

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Keywords: *Nanoclay, Composite, Polymer, Fire*

1 Introduction

Nanoparticles from clay have been well known as a potential precursor of nanocomposites because of the significant improvement in mechanical properties and their availability [1]. Nanoclay contains very thin layers of silicates, in which the octahedral sheet of alumina is sandwiched between two tetrahedral sheets of silica. Montmorillonite (MMT) nanoclay, the most widely used type, or smectites group is formed when Al-atom in the octahedral sheet is partially substituted by Mg-cation, thus pristine MMT clay is hydrophilic. MMT is often treated with cation-organic surfactants to render it organophilic.

Since the discovery of nanoclay in the 1900s, many research projects have been conducted to investigate the enhancement of nanoclay at low replacement levels (less than 5%) on properties of the nanocomposites. Most of them were on the mechanical, electrical and thermal properties. Nanoclay was also found to improve the performance of the composites when exposed to fire. Pavlidou and Papaspyrides [2] stated that the reduction of peak of heat release rate (PHRR) was proportional to the percentage of clay in resin such as polyurethane (PU), polyethylene (PE), and ethylene vinyl acetate (EVA). With low concentration of nanoclay (2-5%), the heat release rate (HRR) of EVA-based nanocomposites reduced by 70%, whereas Cloisite 30B accounted for 50% reduction in PHRR. Varley et al. [3] added Nanomer 1.34TCN (from Nanocor) to neat Nylon-6 using the twin screw extruder. The fire performance of the composites was observed per the cone calorimetry measurement according to ASTM E1354-1992 with the heat flux of 35 kW/m². The sample processed at 220°C showed a reduction of 41% PHRR and required longer time to finish the combustion in comparison with the neat resin. The sample without nanoclay was burnt in the bubbly state while a layer of char was formed over the surface of sample with 5% nanoclay soon after the ignition. This newly formed layer was claimed to suppress the

combustion. Awad et al. [4] investigated the effect of bentonite in PVC-based nanocomposites. The cone calorimeter at a heat flux of 50kW/m² was applied to evaluate the fire retardancy of the composites. The PHRR of the nanocomposite reduced to 233 kW/m² (70%) at the replacement level of 2% by weight. In another research by Mohanty and Nayak [5], organically modified clay Cloisite 30B treated with methyl tallow bis-2-hydroxyethyl ammonium and Cloisite 20A treated with dimethyl-dihydrogenated tallow ammonium were used with Poly(methyl methacrylate) (PMMA). The flammability of the exfoliated nanocomposite was investigated by UL-94. A reduction of burning rate by 25 – 30% for samples containing nanoclay was observed. Fina et al. [6] used the twin screw extruder to blend the unmodified clay and organomodified clay Cloisite 20A into PP at the concentration of 5%. At the incident flux of 50 kW/m², the PHRR of the nanocomposite containing Cloisite 20A was reduced by over 50%, whereas a reduction of only 25% was observed in the case of unmodified clay composite.

The effect of nanoclay on the fire retardancy of thermosetting resin based composites has also been investigated. Liu et al. [7] dispersed organo-modified clay Nanocor I.30 into epoxy with different hardeners. The composites were tested under the cone calorimetry at the heat flux of 50 kW/m². The sample of bisphenol A epoxy/diethyl toluene diamine (as the hardener) and 5% nanoclay compassed a PHRR 16.5% lower than the neat resin. However, the laminates with nanoclay showed more severe combustion. The reason for this may lie in the dispersing technique as nanoclay and the resin was mixed mechanically for 1 h. The performance of the nanocomposite was known to depend to a great extent on the dispersion of the nanoparticles in the mixture and properties of composites with poorly dispersed nanoclay were witnessed to fall in the same range as traditional microcomposites [2].

In this study, the effect of organoclay on the fire performance of the hybrid nano composite was

investigated. Three types of thermosetting resin and two types of clay were used to study their impact on the fire retardancy. Taguchi DoE method was applied to evaluate statistically the significance of those parameters to the fire retardancy of the composite.

2 Experimental details

2.1 Materials

Unsaturated polyester Polyplex and vinyl ester SPV636 were obtained from Nuplex Australia. Methyl ethyl ketone peroxide (MEKP) and CHM50 (cumyl hydroperoxide) were used as the catalysts, respectively. A constant ratio by weight of the resin system and the catalyst was chosen for all samples. Epoxy (Kinetix R118) purchased from ATL Composites was used as the third resin. Kinetix R118 contains bisphenol A (more than 60% by weight) and bisphenol F. Kinetix R118 is diluted by 1,6-hexanediglycidyl ether an aliphatic glycidylether C12-C14 alcohol. A slow hardener H120 produced by ATL Composites was chosen to be the hardener for Kinetix R118. The gelling time of all resins is within 40-60 minutes at 25°C.

The reinforcement composes of six layers of 418 gsm biaxial E-glass fabrics. The first direction of the fabric weighs 236 gsm while the weight of the second direction is 174 gsm. Biaxial fabrics were chosen, as they are heavier than woven products, which contribute to save the fabrication costs.

Two grades of organophilic clay from Aldrich Sigma Australia were used. Both of them are specially designed for flame retardant purposes. Nanoclay type A is MMT surface-treated with silane coupling agent, while Nanoclay type B uses dimethyl dialkyl (C14-C18) amine as the organic modified agent. The clay nanoparticles of both types are 200-300 nm in lateral dimension and 1nm in thickness. After surface treatment, the clay has the average particle size of 10-11 µm.

2.2 Preparation of nanocomposites

The nanocomposites were prepared by three different procedures as shown in Fig. 1. In procedure A, nanoclay was added gradually to the respective resin and mixed manually for 10 minutes. The compounds were then mixed with the overhead stirrer at room temperature and 500rpm for 2 hours prior to infusion. Procedure B involved the application of ultrasonication energy for mixing. Nanoclay was also added and mixed mechanically for 10 minutes. The mixtures were placed in the bath sonicator at the frequency of 40 kHz for 30 minutes

before adding the catalyst/ hardener. In procedure C, acetone was used as the solvent (50ml acetone per 1gr nanoclay) to disperse nanoclay by ultrasonication before mixing with the resin. Heating is required in this method to remove the solvent. However, this removal process also evaporates styrene and the lost styrene is added in the next step before mixing with the catalyst.

The fabrications of composite laminates were conducted by the infusion system. Six layers of glass fibre fabric were cut to 380 mm x 540 mm and stacked together in the same direction. Only mixtures with epoxy were degassed for 30 minutes at 98% vacuum level in the resin trap. The stack of reinforcement fabrics were laid in the mould and infused with Enka channel/distribution media/peelply as shown in Fig. 2. The infusion proceeded at 98% of vacuum level. For UP-based and vinyl ester-based laminates, the pump was left running overnight before demoulding. For epoxy-based laminates, the pump was off 4 hours after the infusion and the samples were demoulded after 10 hours. All the samples were cured at room temperature and post-cured at 40°C (samples from Polyplex or SPV636) and 80°C (samples from R118) for 5 hours.

2.3 Testing and characterization

Fire retardancy of the composite was evaluated using cone calorimetry in accordance with ISO 5660-1 (Fig. 3). Samples were tested in horizontal orientation. They were cut from post-cured panels to the size of 100x100x3mm and exposed to 50 kW/m² radiant cone. Samples of each composition were tested with ±10% reproducibility. Thermal resistant wool was utilized to prevent heat loss from samples to the stainless steel holder. The thickness of the wool was designed to ensure the distance between the upper surface of samples and the pilot igniter is 25mm. Heavy aluminium foils were carefully wrapped over the lower surface and vertical sides of the samples so no liquid resin could flow out of the combustion zone. In all tests, the pilot igniter was removed immediately after the continuous flame occurred.

2.4 Taguchi method

Taguchi method is known as a modern and economic approach for experimental planning based on statistical design [8]. It is a fractional factorial experimental design, which chooses a fraction of the total combinations in the design space. This method

develops the orthogonal array to investigate the factors independently.

Four factors of 2-3 levels were used as shown in Table 1. This method offers a set of 9 trials (Table 2) instead of 54 full-factorial trials to cover all the experiments. Signal-to-noise (S/N) ratio is defined as the critical parameter to evaluate the effect of each factor on the final characteristics. Minimizing and maximizing functions are used depending on the object of the optimization. The former is for minimizing the final characteristics while the latter is for maximizing. The functions are defined as follows:

$$S / N_{\text{minimizing}} = -10 \log \left(\sum_{i=1}^{N_i} \frac{Y_i}{N_i} \right)$$

$$S / N_{\text{maximizing}} = -10 \log \left(\frac{1}{N_i} \sum_{i=1}^{N_i} \frac{1}{Y_i^2} \right)$$

where N_i is the number of trial experiments
 Y_i is the characteristic value at trial i

The S/N ratio of each factor and level is then calculated as the average from those S/N ratios. The wider S/N range reflects the higher influence of the factor on the final characteristics.

3 Results and discussions

3.1 Fibre to resin weight ratio

The fibre to resin weight ratio is determined by burning the laminates. This ratio is affected by the rheology of the resin, permeability of the reinforcement and the applied vacuum level. In the fabrication process, vacuum level is maintained at 98% for all samples. The glass reinforcements are also similar in all laminates. Thus resin viscosity and flowability are the main parameters having influence on this ratio. Higher percentage of reinforcement, i.e. high fibre to resin weight ratio contributes to better performance of the laminate in fire as glass reinforcement does not burn in tested conditions. As can be seen from Table 3, the percentage of fibre weight in the laminates falls in the range from 58% to 65%. Fig. 4 shows the S/N ratio of fibre weight percentage in the laminates. Resin type, clay type and clay content have high impact on this ratio while the fabrication procedure has least effect. Polyplex, SPV636 and R118 have different viscosities, thus result in high influence. Two clay types, are treated with different surfactants. The surfactants act as the bridge between the inorganic clay and the organic resin. The lower S/N ratio (36.6) of samples with

nanoclay type B shows small flowability of the mixed resin with this type.

3.2 Heat release rate (HRR), peak of heat release rate (PHRR) and time to reach PHRR (T_p)

HRR curves of the samples are shown in Fig. 5, Fig. 7 and Table 3. Polyester-based and vinyl ester-based laminates have very similar curves with PHRR below 400 kW/m², while epoxy-based laminates has PHRR of well above 500 kW/m². The highest effect of nanoclay on lowering PHRR was observed with 5% nanoclay in epoxy-based composites, which is 15% lower than PHRR of epoxy-based sample with 1-3% of nanoclay.

Fig. 6 shows S/N ratios of PHRR, T_p and PHRR/ T_p . PHRR is an important parameter of materials in fire incidents as it expresses the highest heat flux that material contributes to the fire. Higher PHRRs are observed with more combustible materials and thus are more critical to be used. As can be seen from Fig. 6a, the type of resin has the highest influence on PHRR of the laminates. Epoxy-based composites have very high S/N ratios which means R188 is not very suitable for applications where minimal flammability is required. Nanoclay type has the smallest effect on PHRR, however nanoclay type B is slightly better than type with a S/N ratio of 5% lower. Clay content and fabrication procedure have similar effect on PHRR. The ranges of S/N for both are from 52.3 to 53.4. Procedure B and 5% clay are two points that reach the minimum values in the two S/N lines. Both procedure B and C involve sonication energy; hence the distribution of clay in the matrix is enhanced. However, the presence of the volatile solvent in procedure C may contribute to higher S/N values of PHRR. It shows that 2 hours of heating at 55°C is not enough to evaporate all the solvents. Further heat treatment may be applied but it is a challenge to use this method in large-scale production because of the time constraint. S/N ratios of T_p are calculated in order to maximize T_p as longer T_p leads to better fire performance. In practice, longer T_p is important as materials with lower PHRR requires longer time to reach its peak of heat emission, thus allowing more time for evacuation. The trends are quite similar between PHRR and T_p except for procedure. Samples produced by procedure C have the highest T_p . This can be explained by the application of both sonication energy and organic solvent help to distribute nanoclay more evenly in the resin, therefore, some kind of nanoclay matrix is formed in

the resin and lengthens the time to reach PHRR of the laminates.

3.3 Total heat release (THR) and heat of combustion

THR and heat of combustion are two other important fire parameters of materials. Fig. 8 shows THR and heat of combustion of all the samples. PHRR and T_p respectively show the maximum contribution of the material combustion to the fire and the necessary time to trigger that peak. THR reflects the total contribution of the materials to the flame. THR is the overall heat per area that a material can emit during its combustion. Heat of combustion is also the heat released from the combusted material; however, heat of combustion is determined with each weight unit. THR and heat of combustion are strictly considered in many building applications as the total heat emitted from the burning material critically results in the level of structural damage. Therefore, S/N ratio of THR and heat of combustion are calculated according to the minimizing function.

S/N ratios of THR and heat of combustion are illustrated in Fig. 9. Clay type again has the smallest effect on both THR and heat of combustion. There is a reverse trend between the two: nanoclay type A contributes to lower THR while samples with nanoclay type B have smaller heat of combustion. The lower THR of samples with type A, however, is because of the high fibre weight percentage as discussed in section 3.1. Similar trend can be found in the variation of S/N ratios of resin type and fabrication procedure.

A significant impact of clay content is observed here, while the effect of clay content is quite low (only 20% compared to the maximum S/N ratio range). Clay content has the highest influence on THR and that effect is the second highest with heat of combustion. Both THR and heat of combustion show that nanoclay is effective with the weight percentage in the resin of 5%. Samples with 1% and 3% of nanoclay have very similar S/N ratios of THR and heat of combustion while that of samples with 5% nanoclay is comparatively lower. C2 (unsaturated polyester-based resin with 5% nanoclay) has the THR of 90% of C1 (unsaturated polyester-based resin with 5% nanoclay) while C8 (epoxy-based resin with 5% nanoclay) has the THR of around 66% as that of C7 and C9 (epoxy-based resin with 1-3% nanoclay). However, this effect shows that higher percentage of nanoclay in the composite should be further investigated. With

higher amount of nanoclay in the composite, it can form a denser matrix and the formation of the ceramic mineral from clay is more likely to happen.

3.4 Smoke production

Smoke production rate (SPR), total smoke production (TSP), carbon monoxide yield and carbon dioxide yield are shown in Fig. 10 and Table 4. Epoxy-based composites have the lowest TSR (all epoxy-based samples have TSP of lower than $1200 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^2$ while all other samples have TSP of higher than $1200 \text{ m}^2/\text{m}^2$). The clay content also has some influence on TSP with the lowest TSP is observed with samples of 5% clay in each resin group.

4 Conclusions

The effect of nanoclay on the flame retardancy of glass fibre reinforced composites is investigated in this work. The experiments are designed according to Taguchi DoE to define the level of effect of resin type, clay type, clay content and fabrication procedure. Three types of thermosettings are used and they are found to be the group with highest impact on PHRR and T_p of the composites. Clay type and fabrication process have major effect on THR and heat of combustion of the composites. The addition of clay at 5% contributes to reduce PHRR, THR and heat of combustion of the composites; however, more tests are required with higher percentage of clay to comprehensively evaluate the effect of clay on fire performance of the composites. Procedure C can provide good distribution of clay in the resin, however, the remaining solvent lower its effectiveness. Although longer treatment with heat is proposed to minimize the amount of organic solvent, this method is limited in terms of time consumption and cost effectiveness. Further work on the rheology and microstructure of the laminates is necessary and this work is continuing at the University of Melbourne.

Acknowledgements

Authors like to acknowledge the assistance provided by Dr Jinghan Lu in fabricating the specimens. The assistance provided by Dr Khalid Moinuddin of Centre for Environmental Safety and Risk Engineering at Victoria University in helping to conduct Calorimeter tests is acknowledged. The experimental work is conducted with the assistance of ARC Linkage Grant LP110100429. The research support from Australian Research Council and Permasteelisa Ltd is also acknowledged.

Fig. 1 Preparation of nanocomposites

Fig. 2 Arrangement for resin infusion process, (a) Schematic of the infusion system, (b) photos of the infusion setup

Fig. 3 Schematic of cone calorimetry test

Fig. 4 S/N ratio of fibre weight percentage in the laminates

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Fig. 5 HRR curves of samples exposed to Cone calorimeter tests vs. time

Fig. 6 S/N ratio of (a) PHRR, (b) T_p and (c) PHRR/ T_p

Fig. 7 PHRR, T_p and PHRR/T_p ratio

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Fig. 8 THR and heat of combustions of the samples

Fig. 9 S/N ratio of (a) THR and (b) heat of combustion

Fig. 10 SPR of the samples

Table 1. Factors and levels used in L₉ DoE layout

Level	Factor			
	Resin	Clay type	Clay content	Procedure
1	UP	Type A	1%	A
2	Vinyl ester	Type B	3%	B
3	Epoxy	-	5%	C

Table 2. L₉ orthogonal array

Sample	Composition (%)			Fabrication
	Resin	Catalyst/hardener	Nanoclay	
C1	98% Polyplex	1% MEKP	1%	A
C2	96% Polyplex	1% MEKP	3%	B
C3	94% Polyplex	1% MEKP	5%	C
C4	96% SPV636	1% CHM50	3%	C
C5	94% SPV636	1% CHM50	5%	A
C6	98% SPV636	1% CHM50	1%	B
C7	75% R118	20% H120	1%	B
C8	79% R118	20% H120	5%	C
C9	77% R118	20% H120	3%	A

Table 3. Fibre to resin ratio and heat release from cone calorimeter tests

Sample	Fibre to resin	PHRR	T _p	PHRR /T _p
		kW/m ²	sec	kW/m ² s
C1	62:38	416	68	6.22
C2	60:40	349	70	4.69
C3	62:38	365	79	4.65
C4	63:37	405	82	4.94
C5	65:35	352	85	4.25
C6	63:37	354	86	4.13
C7	61:39	672	80	8.37
C8	65:35	568	70	8.20
C9	58:42	673	77	8.79

Table 4. Smoke release, carbon monoxide yield and carbon dioxide yield

Sample	TSR	CO _y	CO _{2 y}
	m ² /m ²	kg/kg	kg/kg
C1	1242	0.0645	1.82
C2	1366	0.0704	2.26
C3	1206	0.0794	2.40
C4	1499	0.1119	2.66
C5	1341	0.0801	1.67
C6	1503	0.0832	2.30
C7	1196	0.0865	2.42
C8	902	0.0770	2.35
C9	1199	0.0746	1.66

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